

“Tagay” and Cross Contact Contamination: The Cebuano Culture of Sharing Glasses

Brian A. Vasquez
University of the Visayas
Mandaue City

Abstract

The purpose of the study was to analyze the culture-based practice of “tagay” among Cebuanos. This ethnographic study obtained information from the lay Cebuanos in their own cultural context. Twenty-five were selected purposively from the pool of potential informants and 12 from the 25 were chosen purposively as key informants. Theory building metasynthesis on the ill-effects associated with sharing of utensils was done after documenting and analyzing the practice. The researcher observed that in Cebu City, drinking alcoholic beverages was done by sharing glasses. Each one takes turn in drinking and this is called “tagay”. Variations from the traditional practice were also observed. These were: (1) passing two glasses in round-robin style; (2) passing the drink under the table; and (3) passing the glass on the next table. Medical and paramedical professionals were also observed in the practice of sharing glasses during drinking sessions. Systematic reviews of related studies revealed that this practice, be it traditional or contemporary, may result in transmission of communicable diseases or cross contamination of allergen. Culture Care Theory helped in the analysis of the practice to arrive in a well-thought nursing intervention plan. Health teaching guide was drafted to be utilized for community, small group and classroom instructions. Modification of the practice by: (1) using individual glasses; and (2) passing the bottle instead of the glass; preserves the cultural practice while preventing its ill-effects. Contents of the health teaching guide were translated in a video advertisement format.

Background of the Study

After a long hard day's work, Cebuanos look forward to an evening of relaxation with friends, perhaps to reaffirm with one another. Part of the Cebuano social and divertional activities is “tagay”. Alcoholic beverages are an indispensable part of the Cebuano occasions. Valbuano (2001) commented that even when there is no special occasion, many hang out together in the streets, in front of their houses and convenience stores drinking low-cost alcoholic beverages. This is particularly true in a low income community where, unlike those from the middle and high income brackets who hangs out in bars and drink considerably expensive alcoholic beverages.

Literally, the word “tagay” means bottoms up, but the term refers to a rap and drinking session performed by a group of men gathered around a small table, usually in front of the barrio sari-sari store, or in someone's backyard (Reyes, 2004). However, among Cebuanos the term is referred to as the act of drinking round-robin style using a common glass (iGuide Interactive Travel Guide, 2010). One is supposed to drink bottoms-up before passing the glass to the next person. This custom is known as “tagayay” and one person usually volunteers to pour the drink.

Declining an invitation to a “tagay” is unheard of (Reyes, 2004). “Tagay” is just one of the many Cebuano cultural traditions that define the value of “pakigkauban” (sense of comradeship). Saying “no” is a form of disrespect among Cebuanos.

There is a need to document the Cebuano practice of “tagay” since it is not well documented. Documenting the cultural practice allows others to evaluate the safety of the cultural practice. There is a need to narratively acknowledge this practice and link it with available literatures and studies by doing a systematic review to provide nurses basis for their decisions and actions in their provision of care.

According to medical practitioners, the practice of the Cebuano “tagay” can lead to some ill-effects. The researcher personally considers the practice unhygienic. Some Cebuanos unknowing or denyably know that some diseases or fod allergens can be transmitted through indirect contact. This occurs when a susceptible person comes in contact with a contaminated object (Longworth, 2001). This

“Tagay” and Cross Contact Contamination: The Cebuano Culture of Sharing Glasses

Brian A. Vasquez
University of the Visayas
Mandaue City

Abstract

The purpose of the study was to analyze the culture-based practice of “tagay” among Cebuanos. This ethnographic study obtained information from the lay Cebuanos in their own cultural context. Twenty-five were selected purposively from the pool of potential informants and 12 from the 25 were chosen purposively as key informants. Theory building metasynthesis on the ill-effects associated with sharing of utensils was done after documenting and analyzing the practice. The researcher observed that in Cebu City, drinking alcoholic beverages was done by sharing glasses. Each one takes turn in drinking and this is called “tagay”. Variations from the traditional practice were also observed. These were: (1) passing two glasses in round-robin style; (2) passing the drink under the table; and (3) passing the glass on the next table. Medical and paramedical professionals were also observed in the practice of sharing glasses during drinking sessions. Systematic reviews of related studies revealed that this practice, be it traditional or contemporary, may result in transmission of communicable diseases or cross contamination of allergen. Culture Care Theory helped in the analysis of the practice to arrive in a well-thought nursing intervention plan. Health teaching guide was drafted to be utilized for community, small group and classroom instructions. Modification of the practice by: (1) using individual glasses; and (2) passing the bottle instead of the glass; preserves the cultural practice while preventing its ill-effects. Contents of the health teaching guide were translated in a video advertisement format.

Background of the Study

After a long hard day's work, Cebuanos look forward to an evening of relaxation with friends, perhaps to reaffirm with one another. Part of the Cebuano social and divertional activities is “tagay”. Alcoholic beverages are an indispensable part of the Cebuano occasions. Valbuano (2001) commented that even when there is no special occasion, many hang out together in the streets, in front of their houses and convenience stores drinking low-cost alcoholic beverages. This is particularly true in a low income community where, unlike those from the middle and high income brackets who hangs out in bars and drink considerably expensive alcoholic beverages.

Literally, the word “tagay” means bottoms up, but the term refers to a rap and drinking session performed by a group of men gathered around a small table, usually in front of the barrio sari-sari store, or in someone's backyard (Reyes, 2004). However, among Cebuanos the term is referred to as the act of drinking round-robin style using a common glass (iGuide Interactive Travel Guide, 2010). One is supposed to drink bottoms-up before passing the glass to the next person. This custom is known as “tagayay” and one person usually volunteers to pour the drink.

Declining an invitation to a “tagay” is unheard of (Reyes, 2004). “Tagay” is just one of the many Cebuano cultural traditions that define the value of “pakigkauban” (sense of comradeship). Saying “no” is a form of disrespect among Cebuanos.

There is a need to document the Cebuano practice of “tagay” since it is not well documented. Documenting the cultural practice allows others to evaluate the safety of the cultural practice. There is a need to narratively acknowledge this practice and link it with available literatures and studies by doing a systematic review to provide nurses basis for their decisions and actions in their provision of care.

According to medical practitioners, the practice of the Cebuano “tagay” can lead to some ill-effects. The researcher personally considers the practice unhygienic. Some Cebuanos unknowing or denyably know that some diseases or fod allergens can be transmitted through indirect contact. This occurs when a susceptible person comes in contact with a contaminated object (Longworth, 2001). This

undoubtedly can happen in the Cebuano "tagay".

Marian Calago (2009) a blogger from Cebu, quoted, "I had a neighbor who was admitted to a public general hospital for difficulty in breathing. The admission took a couple of days in the hospital. Before he was admitted, he was then a so-called "tambay" in our barangay. He used to stay often with his friends house to drink overnight. He was sharing a glass to his "katambay" (friends who hang out with) without knowing that one of his colleagues has an uncured disease".

The researcher analyzed the practice of "tagay" and the health problems that can be harbored in the practice. The results of this study will help nurses understand the Cebuano cultural practice of "tagay". This will be very helpful in formulating a well-thought culturally-based health teaching guide to prevent its ill-effects.

Theoretical Framework

Nurses interact with people of similar as well as diverse cultural backgrounds in the social health care delivery system. People may have similar or different frames of reference regarding their health and health care needs. Acknowledging and adapting to the cultural needs of patients and significant others are important components of nursing care (Smeltzer et al, 2008).

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of the Theoretical Framework based from the Sunrise Model of Madeleine Leininger. This is modified to suit the need for this study.

Nurses could not exclusively rely in their personal practices. It is necessary for these nurses to be aware of the collection of traditional expressions to which their clients subscribe. Sensitivity in rendering care is essential to meet the various levels and depths of the client's traditional expressions and needs. The client's expression with what is seen as traditional is multifaceted and individual. Thus, each client has to be approached, taking into consideration their unique needs (Kozier, 2004).

Madeleine Leininger (2001), founder of the specialty called transcultural nursing, writes that culture involves learned and transmitted knowledge about values, beliefs, rules of behavior, and lifestyle practices that guide designated groups in their thinking and patterned ways. Culture develops over time and intellectual and artistic manifestations, and each individual person, including each nurse, is culturally unique (Giger & Davidhizar, 2004). Dwyer (2006) adjoined that caring for a person involves exploring the spiritual beliefs, and values of that person. Using the nursing process, the health care provider would assess the client, plan and deliver a culturally sensitive intervention and evaluate the result.

According to Dwyer (2006), in order to proceed through the nursing process, the nurse must have a framework with which to start. This would be a map to navigate the course through the clinical journey. In order to choose a practical method for this process, an examination of several frameworks helped in the final choice. Since the Cebuano health belief system is deeply tied with culture and that their "tagay" practices are different from other cultures, the researcher aims to understand the Cebuano "tagay" practices with the aid of Madeleine Leininger's Culture Care Theory. This theory is based on the belief that people of different cultures inform and are capable of guiding professionals to receive the kind of care they desire or need (Alligood & Tomey, 2002). Leininger affirms that care is the core of nursing and this is the heart of the model. Leininger manages to unify nursing, the nursing process and caring. This combination results in the optimal process of developing cultural sensitivity and treatment.

Leininger recognized insufficiency in the nursing practice, the deficiency of cultural awareness. Leininger's pioneering work combined concepts from anthropology and nursing, merging culture and nursing care. The transformation resulted in a more holistic nursing view, in contrast to the traditional medical model (Alligood & Tomey, 2002). The professional nurse must understand, embrace and respect these culturally based beliefs and practices in order to provide culturally congruent care. This comprehensive approach would assure the care for the whole person and not just the illness (Dwyer, 2006).

The researcher observed that in Cebu, drinking alcoholic beverages is done by using only one glass. Each one take turn in drinking and this is called "tagay". This practice may pose harm among Cebuano drinkers. The Culture Care Theory will help in analyzing the practice to arrive in a well-thought nursing intervention plan or nursing care decision and action.

Even before Spanish came Filipinos are fond of drinking alcoholic beverages specially "tuba". Morga (1962), a Spanish historian claimed that when he arrived in the Philippines, "the natives of this islands drink this liquor in the day and night without end in their meetings, weddings, feast, circles accompanying by singing by a few who are so inclined and who come to drink and have a good time, although this habit does not carry with it, according to their estimation any dishonor or infamy.

There is a culture surrounding the act of drinking. Filipinos are extremely social and these characteristics extend to sharing drink and "pulutan". The purpose of drinking is to socialize (Rodel, 2002).

One cannot isolate this from cultural practices. Leininger (2002) said that:

"A new way of looking at a new knowledge and practices are essential for nurses to function in a rapidly challenging multi-cultural world. Substantive theory based research knowledge was greatly needed with a global and comparative focus to care for people of diverse culture. Culturally based care knowledge was the major missing area in nursing the mid 20th century and still in some places in the world. I coined the construct of culturally - congruent care."

It is important to study the culture of a particular group to give proper nursing care. Leininger (2002), in her theory culture care diversity and universality, wrote 13 assumptive premises. However there are only six assumptions that are applicable in this study. These are the following: (1) care is the essence of nursing and a distinct, dominant, central and unifying focus; (2) culturally based care (caring) is essentially for well being, health, growth, survival, and in facing handicaps or death; (3) culturally based care is the most comprehensive, holistic, and particularistic means to know, to explain, and predict beneficial congruent care practices; (4) culturally based caring is essential to curing and healing, as there can be no curing without caring, although caring can occur without curing; (5) culture care concepts, meanings, expressions, patterns, processes, and structural forms vary transculturally, with diversities (differences) and some universalities (commonalities); (6) culturally congruent and beneficial nursing care can only occur when care values, expressions, or patterns are known and used explicitly for appropriate, safe, and meaningful care.

The researchers believed that "tagay" is a contributory factor in the transmission of communicable

diseases and food allergens through cross contact contamination. As a nursing practitioner, one should look into new approaches in treating or caring patients. The researchers use an assessment model to guide them in exploring cultural phenomena that might affect nursing care. To achieve this imperative goal, Leininger delineated three elements or care decisions and actions that nurses needed to reflect on in providing culturally congruent care. This included: (1) culture care preservation and maintenance - this occurred when nursing care preservation or maintenance was used to enable people of a particular culture to retain or preserve relevant care values so that they could maintain their well-being, recover from illness, or face handicaps and/or death; (2) culture care accommodation or negotiation - this involved the actions and decisions that help people in a culture adapt to or negotiate with others for a beneficial or satisfying health outcome with professional care providers; (3) culture care repatterning or restructuring - this was used to help clients change or modify their health care patterns to provide a way of life more beneficial or healthier while still respecting their cultural patterns and beliefs (Alligood & Tomey, 2002; Kozier et al, 2004; Shives, 2008).

Cultural congruent nursing care was the central idea and goal of Leininger theory. Nursing care was based on cultural values, beliefs and practices of an individual or group; the acts or decision which support, facilitate, and enable the nurse in providing meaningful, beneficial, and satisfying care that led to health and well being (Alligood & Tomey, 2002). Incorporating cultural care preservation, accommodation and repatterning into nursing plan of care allowed for meaningful quality of care. This was accomplished through the inclusion of important cultural values while assisting the patient to modify practices in ways to attain their optimal levels of wellness and quality of life working for the optimal outcome.

Using the Sunrise Model is helpful to the author to guide the process of understanding the Cebuano culture. The statement, *"let the sun rise"* figuratively mean to have nurses open their minds in order to discover many different factors influencing care and ultimately the health and well being of clients.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of the study was to analyze the culture-based practice of *"tagay"* among Cebuanos.

Specifically, the study attempted to answer the following questions:

1. How was *"tagay"* practiced among Cebuanos?
2. Basing from the metasynthesis of related studies on sharing utensils, what different forms of cross contact contamination were identified and linked to the lived practice of *"tagay"* among Cebuanos?
3. What health teaching plan was drafted based from the findings of the study?

Research Method

This study employed the qualitative design utilizing in-depth analysis to provide accurate descriptions to document the lived practice of *"tagay"* among Cebuanos through fieldwork. Furthermore, this utilized ethn nursing method which applied ethnography in nursing. This qualitative study has an anthropological viewpoint to delineate the Cebuano practice of *"tagay"* as a culturally and professionally determined phenomenon.

This ethnographic study obtained information from the lay Cebuanos in their own cultural context. With the ethn nursing method based on emic (insider's views) beliefs, the researcher reached to the discovery of grounded or people-based concept of care and well-being (Alligood & Tomey, 2002). The data collected were used to analyze *"tagay"* from the cultural actor's point of view, aiming to elicit meaning and understanding through interpretation of their behavior. The researcher's etic (outsider's views) perspective on *"tagay"* with professional nursing knowledge confirmed and supplemented the analysis of data. This knowledge helped guide in drafting a culturally-congruent health teaching guide for Cebuanos in their practice of *"tagay"*. Retrospective analysis was also considered.

Theory building metasynthesis or systematic review of qualitative research studies and literatures on the ill-effects associated with sharing of utensils were done after documenting and analyzing the practice of the Cebuano *"tagay"*. It was the researcher's assumption that the diseases associated with sharing of utensils were similar to those of *"tagay"*.

Thorne and colleagues (2004), as cited by Polit and Beck (2008), acknowledged the diversity and used the term theory building metasynthesis as an umbrella term to broadly represent a family of

methodological approaches to developing new knowledge based on rigorous analysis of existing qualitative research findings and literature. This served as the first part of theory building as an output of this study. Finfgeld (2003) and Schreiber and colleagues (1997), also cited by Polit and Beck (2008), described a typology of theory building metasynthesis that puts the role of theory at center stage: (1) theory building; (2) theory explication; and (3) theory description.

Environment

The study was conducted in the city of Cebu. Cebu City is the capital city of Cebu and the second city in the Philippines, the second most significant metropolitan centre in the Philippines and known as the oldest city in the country. The city is located on the eastern shore of Cebu. According to the 2007 Philippine census, the city has a population of about 798,809 people. The urban style of "tagay" will be documented in this area which is the evolution of the oldway of doing the "tagay".

Informants and Sampling Procedure

Informants and Sampling Procedure for Ethnonursing. The researcher approached potential Cebuano lay informants through the help of trusted individuals, known as "gatekeepers". These participants were: (1) residents of Cebu City for at least thirteen years since birth; (2) born and reared in the City of Cebu; (3) at least thirteen years old; (4) have not lived outside Cebu City; and (5) currently practicing "tagay" for at least one year.

The researcher employed the "big net" approach, conveniently mingled and conversed with as many members per community. Twenty-five informants per community were selected purposively from the pool of potential informants. Although there were only twenty-five, twelve key informants were selected purposively, guided by the ethnographer's judgments.

Sampling Qualitative Materials for Meta-Synthesis. Thirty two related studies and literature were reviewed systematically. Basing on the assumption that diseases brought about by sharing of utensils were likely the same with the diseases that were acquired during Cebuano "tagay" sessions, the related studies and literature reviewed systematically were all about the diseases that are acquired in sharing utensils.

Research Instruments

The main instrument of the study was the researcher himself. The concept of researcher as instrument was used frequently to describe the significant role ethnographers play in analyzing and interpreting a culture (Polit & Beck, 2008). It utilized ethnonursing enablers, and related studies and literature for theory building metasynthesis.

Since the first part of the study was ethnonursing in nature, it utilized different enablers to discover specific data related to theory tenets and for in-depth data of overt, covert, unknown, or ambiguous nursing phenomena. Instead of instruments, Leininger formulated enablers to discover truths. Enablers sharply contrast with mechanistic devices such as tools, scales, measurement instruments, and other impersonal objective distancing tools generally used in quantitative studies. Different enablers utilized were:

1. Leininger's Observation-Participation-Reflection Enabler. The following phases were observed: (1) Primarily Observation and Active Listening (no active participation); (2) Primarily Observation with Limited Participation; (3) Primarily Participation with Continued Observations; and (4) Primarily Reflection and Reconfirmation of Findings with Informants.
2. Leininger's Stranger to Trusted Friend Enabler. The goal was to become a trusted friend: the process of moving from becoming a stranger to a trusted friend. This took time and keen sensitivity while showing genuine interest in the Cebuano informants and respecting their ideas, beliefs, responses, and cultural ideas about the concept of "tagay".
3. Sunrise Model Enabler. This model originally has three tenets. For this study, it was modified and presented in a schematic diagram as shown in Figure 1.
4. Enabler 4 is the Specific Domain of Inquiry Enabler. This was developed by the researcher doing the study: this is specific to the researcher's interests and focused on the domain of study. These were already presented in the statement of the problem and specific questions.

Materials for Meta-Synthesis. Related studies and literatures were reviewed systematically. Since the Cebuano practice of "tagay" involved sharing of glasses, results of studies and literature related to

sharing of utensils were reviewed qualitatively and linked to the Cebuano practice of Tagay. This was based on the assumption that diseases brought about by sharing of utensils are likely the same with the diseases that can be acquired during Cebuano Tagay sessions.

Research Procedures

There were four stages namely: Stage 1 - Preliminary survey with anticipatory fieldwork; Stage 2 - Documentation of the Cebuano practice of "tagay" in both rural and urban communities; Stage 3 - Theory Building metasyntesis of related studies and related literature on sharing of utensils, and linking its ill-effects to the practice of the Cebuano "tagay"; and Stage 4 - Formulation and Application of Health Teaching through a video advertistment. Specific activities per stages are presented in a matrix as shown below.

Matrix 1
Stages of Research Project

Stages of the Research Project	Data and Data Collection Methods	Method of Analysis
Stage 1 Preliminary survey with anticipatory fieldwork	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Gathered written information ➤ Gathered pictorial descriptive information ➤ Preliminary personal tour ➤ Gained familiarity with the ambiance ➤ Noted major activities ➤ Identified "gatekeeper" of the community ➤ Found potential participants for the study 	Content analysis of pertinent data for overview, procedure guidelines and supportive data.
Stage 2 Documenting the Cebuano practice of "Tagay"	<p>Interviews of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Residents (N=25; 12 out from the 25 as key informants) <p>Field Observations:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. primary observation and active listening; 2. primary observation with limited participation; 3. primary participation with continuing observation; and 4. primary reflection and reconfirmation of results of informants 	<p>Ethnonursing and content analysis of interviews, participatory observations and reflections.</p> <p>Content Analysis:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) made descriptions of documented raw data from interviews, participatory observation, reflections and diaries; (2) identified descriptions in relation to the view of care; (3) discovered and formulated repetitive patterns of care and analyzed the context in which they occurred; and (4) abstracted major themes, presented findings and drafted major constructs of care aided with documents from the different culture care models, medical models and ethnographic books
Stage 3 Theory Building Metasyntesis	Thirty Two related studies and literatures were reviewed systematically. Since the Cebuano practice of "tagay" involved sharing of glasses, results of studies related to sharing of utensils were reviewed qualitatively and linked to the Cebuano practice of Tagay.	
Stage 4 Formulation and Application of Health Teaching	Contents of the Health Teaching Guide were drafted and translated into a video advertistment format. It will be shown to the different communities, schools and clinics.	

Data Analysis

Ethnonursing Data Analysis. This study utilized Leininger's (2006) ethnonursing qualitative data analysis. This helped facilitate a systematic data analysis. The four phases provided a systematic data analysis. Data from key and general informants with all interviews, observations, ethnohistory data,

social structure factors, generic and professional data, and other data were computer processed, coded, and classified for final analysis at each phase of analysis with final themes.

The first two phases of data analysis included recording of all grounded data along with specific code indicators. The third and fourth phases of data analysis required that the researcher identified recurrent patterns (third phase) and themes (fourth phase).

First Phase involved collecting, describing, and documenting raw data with field journal and electronic documentation. The researcher collected, described, recorded, and begun to collect data related to the purposes, domain of inquiry, or questions under study. This included: (1) recording interview data from key and general informants; (2) making observations and having participatory experiences; (3) identifying contextual meanings; (3) making preliminary interpretations; (4) identifying symbols; (5) recording data related to the phenomena under study, from an emic focus, but attentive to etic data; and (6) data from the condensed and full field journal is processed directly into the computer, coded by hand.

Second Phase involved identification and categorization of descriptors and components. Data were coded and classified as related to the domain of inquiry and sometimes the questions. Emic and etic descriptors were studied within context for similarities and differences. Recurrent components were studied for their meanings.

Third Phase involved pattern and contextual analysis. Data were scrutinized to discover saturated ideas and recurrent patterns of similar or different meanings, expressions, structural forms, interpretations, or explanations of data related to the domain of inquiry. Data were examined to show patterns with respect to meanings in-context and along with further credibility and confirmation of findings.

Fourth Phase involved major themes, research findings, theoretical formulations, and recommendations. This was the highest phase of data analysis, synthesis, and interpretation. It required synthesis of thinking, configurations, analysis, interpreting findings, and creative formulations from data of the previous phases. The researcher abstracted and presented major themes, research findings, recommendations, and theoretical formulations

Theory Building Metasynthesis Data Analysis: The Noblit and Hare Approach (1988 as cited in Polit & Beck, 2008). This approach for synthesizing qualitative studies included seven phases that overlap and repeat as the theory building metasynthesis progresses, the first three of which were preanalytic (1) deciding on the phenomenon; (2) deciding which studies were relevant for the synthesis, and (3) reading and re-reading each literature and study. Phases four to six concerned the analysis: (4) deciding how the studies were related to each other; (5) translating the qualitative studies into one another; and (6) synthesizing translations. Phase 7 or the final phase expressed the synthesis through narratives and matrix summary.

Results from Ethnography

Ethnographic analysis identified the following themes as discussed below:

Traditional and Contemporary Cebuano Way of Sharing Drinking Glasses. The art of Cebuano drinking is demonstrated in the common rotating glass. The glass itself is the medium that summarized the Cebuano Culture in the drinking session; it does not matter whether it is a shot, disposable or regular glass, and whether it is passed clockwise (most common) or counter-clockwise. The session is mediated by a "tig-tagay" (the person who pours the beer in the glass and passes it to his companion) who usually commences by pouring the drink in the common glass and takes the first shot before passing it to the next participant. This process allows every participant to know that each one participates in the session.

The "tig-tagay" always uses the line "imu na" (your turn) when passing the glass to the next person. No one is allowed to deny the drink. There were instances that the "tig-tagay" may forget the flow of the glass and the person given the glass would complain, "aku to ganina" (that was my turn), "kaspas gud maabut" (Why is it too fast?), or "hubgun ku nimu" (Are you trying to make me wasted?).

The traditional practice of sharing one glass was observed to be done only in small groups (2 to 5). For bigger groups, two glasses or more were used either by passing it in one direction or both

directions. Sometimes, the glass would meet together depending on the speed of drinking (when the glasses rotate in one direction) or when passed in both directions. This is termed as "mag-abut". If there were more glasses used in a small group, this kind of drinking session is called "hinangul" (greed). In this practice, they get drunk easily.

Another form of variation noted were: (1) passing the common glass under the table; and (2) concealing the drink by mixing it with juice. Both variations were done to conceal the act of drinking. Even though Cebuanos enjoy the "tagay" practice, the social psyche still played a vital role which hindered the open display of behavior.

There were instances observed that rotating glass would not follow the usual route. For instance, one participant would say, "*aku sa' kay uhaw ku kaayu*" (can I have that drink because I'm thirsty): this usually happen when the said participant cannot wait for his turn. Other participants may interpret this as being "*hangul*" (selfish) which may cause group friction. By-passers or someone from the next table, when familiar or interesting were offered to drink using the common glass. This may be a sign of respect or flirtation.

There were cases wherein the glass would skip participants, this happen when someone would deny the drink because he or she already had taken much. Sometimes, the rest of the participants would not allow the person to deny the drink.

"Tagay" and "Ulaw". Cebuanos are typically "mangging-ulawun" (shy). "Ulaw" is a feeling of inferiority, embarrassment, shyness, and alienation. Cebuanos are very sensitive to personal affront. "Ulaw" (shame) is the value that regulates the Cebuanos' social behavior. Just as one is very careful not to be "ma-ulawan" (subjected to embarrassment).

Passing a drink to someone is a form of asking a favor and both parties are careful not to offend each other. If a favor is not granted, the person is obligated to ask for an apology with an explanation that it is not the intention to refuse but rather other factors beyond his control which keeps him or her from doing so. If one fails to provide an explanation, in the fear of being labeled negatively, the person takes the drink. The latter greatly demonstrated how peer control played a role.

"Maulaw man gud ku mubalibad labi na kung labi na ang nihangyu atong higala" (It will be very shameful to refuse especially if those who offered are our friends).

"Mapugus man gud ko... muagi ta, tunulan dayun ta ug basu, 'one shot lang daw'... maulaw man pud ta mubalibad" (When I pass by, they would offer you a shot and force you to drink. I am ashamed to refuse).

Cultural Influence. In all culture, drinking is essentially a social activity. The primary function of drinking is the facilitation of social bonding (The Social Issues Research Centre, 2010). Alcohol is universally associated with celebration, and drinking is, in all cultures, an essential element of festivity. Heath (1991) points out that:

"... just as drinking and its effects are imbedded in other aspects of culture, so are many other aspects of culture imbedded in the act of drinking..."

In all societies, alcoholic beverages are used as powerful and versatile symbolic tools, to construct and manipulate the social world. Cultural research reveals symbolic features of drinking: (1) as labels defining the nature of social situations or events; and (2) as statements of affiliation (Social Issues Research Centre, 2010).

The social drinking practice in Cebu is distinct to other culture. This practice is one of the many expressions of the Cebuano value of "*pakigka-uban*" and the symbolic expression of this is greatly magnified by the use of the common glass.

"*Pakigkauban*" is a smooth interpersonal relationship (Lynch, 1968). This attitude was primarily guided by conformity with the majority (Jocano, 1997). "*Pakigkauban*" could also be decoded as acting with care headed for others as fellow humans. Since Cebuanos has this value of the collective "I" it is usually expressed in the social drinking session by sharing a common glass. Since declining an invitation to a "tagay" using a common glass is unheard of, the sense of comradeship is very much at play whenever and wherever you see a group of men robustly enjoying this ritual. One would interpret such as "*lain*" (roughly translated as indifferent or not one of us), "*arte*" (roughly translated as people who care too much about certain things, in this case hygiene), "*walay rispitu*" (disrespectful), and "*hilas*"

(roughly translated as boastful).

Jocano (1997) articulated several core elements of a Filipino cultural worldview, which appeared pertinent in understanding the Cebuano cultural perspective. Historically, Cebuanos had embraced a worldview based on the primacy of human relationships in the community. These relationships were built on respect and intertwined with this vision was a group consciousness where people often see individuals as extensions of their own being (Llora, 2004; Boholst, 2006). In this context, Cebuanos created and sustained a highly refined system of values to maintain and uphold the stability and integrity of the group. This system was built on principles of smooth relationships and mutual concern among members for each individual's well being and sense of belonging (Agoncillo & Guerrero, 1987; Enriquez, 1994; McBride, 2001). The primacy of group identity and relational harmony is in itself grounded in a vision of the universe that sees life ultimately as harmonious. Key cultural concepts that reflect this worldview would include "pakigkauban".

Michael Tan (2009) quoted:

"As the San Miguel ads go, 'Iba ang may pinagsamahan!' (Roughly, fellowship matters), drinking is important for reinforcing 'barkada' (peer) relations as well as "pakikisama" (tagalog term for 'pakigkauban'), often defined as being able to get along with others, although this can sometimes deteriorate into blind group conformity especially in the context of drinking...."

Common Glass and Health. Cebuanos are aware of the ill-effects that can be harbored in sharing glasses. However, the cultural practice is much more considered than their scientific learning. Some of the participants observed were even medical and paramedical practitioners who were expected to put their health teachings and scientific knowledge into practice.

Quotes from lay informants:

"Kahibalu uy, daghan na man kung nadunggan bahin anang sakit, parihu anang TB. Madawat man na sa atung laway ang kanag sakit sa TB. Sa akung panan-aw murag tinuud man pud nang makatakud nang sakita sa pag gamit lang ug usa ka basu" (I know. I've heard a lot about that disease, like TB. We can get it from our saliva. As what I have observed, I think it's true that the disease can be communicable by using only one glass).

Quotes from medical and paramedical professional informants:

"Some may get Tuberculosis, with just a droplet; the person contaminated will get the disease. To prevent the transmission of communicable diseases, it is expected not to share glasses... But I think this is difficult in our culture where we are used to this practice especially in drinking sessions... We just need to be more cautious in this kind of practice so that the expenses will not be too expensive (if ever one gets the disease)."

"We don't know if companion in drinking has TB. How about the saliva and the sputum? Come to think of it, who would dare to drink with a person with TB?"

"Pareha anang herpes simplex kanang mga oral lesions... (We can get Herpes Simplex like oral lesions).

"Infectious mononucleosis, it spreads through saliva, especially when kissing somebody and through drinking with the same glass or utensils."

"This can be transmitted through fecal and oral route. Like Hepatitis A and B. When we say gastrointestinal, in drinking, we get diarrhea, amoeba and other GIT diseases. We can get amoeba in a dirty glass. We also have enteric and viral problems."

Results from Metasynthesis

The results of metasynthesis revealed that indirect contact contamination can be harbored from sharing a common glass during Cebuano "tagay" sessions. Two major cross contact communication themes were identified: communicable diseases and cross contact allergic reactions. Another important theme identified is nursing culture care repatterning and restructuring.

Drinking, Sharing of Utensils and Communicable Diseases. According to Juliet Gopez-Cervantes, MD in the Health and Medicine portion of the Philippine Star dated January 18, 2009:

"Filipinos love to drink alcoholic beverages, that is. Drinking sessions are seen everywhere everyday along the streets and sidewalks, inside homes, in 'carinderia' and corner sari-sari stores, and even the upmarket bars and bistros. So phenomenal has been the 'tumahan' tradition that it became the undisputed national pastime and social culture of Filipinos. While local folks' love for drinking session might have built many a friendship and warm cockles of good ole acquaintances, it is, at the same time, taking its toll on the drinkers' health."

Linked with the sharing glass session is the possibility of acquiring communicable diseases. This occurs when a susceptible person comes in contact with a contaminated object (Longworth, 2001). This type of contamination is called indirect contact transmission.

According the supplemental notes of Stephen Abedon (2009), indirect contact transmission is a form of contact transmission where transmission occurs from a reservoir via inanimate objects. These objects generally are referred to as fomites. They are basically almost anything an infected individual (or reservoir) can touch, upon which can be left a residue of contagious pathogen. He added that it is more difficult to avoid indirect contact transmission than it is to avoid direct contact transmission. The best way to prevent indirect contact transmission is by: (1) avoiding contact with fomites; (2) avoiding contact of hands with mucous membranes especially when handling or potentially handling fomites; (3) the use of barriers when handling fomites; (4) disinfecting fomites before handling.

The following diseases can be harbored thru sharing a common glass in drinking sessions (this is not the complete list; this is only based on the available literatures and studies systematically reviewed):

Matrix 2

Summary based from Metasynthesis on Diseases Linked with Sharing a Common Glass

Diseases	Source	Synthesis
TB	October 2009 Delay in Tuberculosis Case Detection in Pwani Region, Tanzania: A Cross Sectional Study Esther S. Ngadaya, Godfrey S. Mfinanga, Eliud R. Wandwalo, & Odd Morkve	The following diseases as discussed in the different literatures and studies revealed the association of getting the disease thru sharing of glasses or utensils.
SARS	May 2005 Reflection on SARS Precautions in a Severe Intellectual Disabilities Hospital in Hong Kong S. Y. Wong, W. W. C. Lim, T. L. Que & D. M. Y. Au	
Pertussis	May 2008 MDCH Vaccine-Preventable Disease Investigation Guidelines – Pertussis	
Norovirus	September 2005 Infection Control Recommendations for Prevention of Transmission of Diarrheal Diseases in Evacuation Centers Department of Health and Human Services: Center for Control and Prevention	
Mumps	November 2008 Mumps Washington State Department of Health	
Meningococcal	March 2009 Meningococcal Disease Information for the Public	It is highly recommended to avoid sharing glasses and utensils, and observe strict hand hygiene (proper hand washing technique).
Viral and Bacterial Meningitis	Nd Facts about Meningitis HARFORD COUNTY HEALTH DEPARTMENT	
Influenza	2010 CDC Guidance on Helping Child Care and Early Childhood Programs Respond to Influenza during the 2009–2010 Influenza Season	

Helicobacter Pylori	June 2001 Helicobacter pylori: Has the killer Escaped from the Institution? A Possible Cause of Increased Stomach Cancer in a Population with Intellectual Disability M. Duff, M. Scheepers, M. Cooper, M. Hoghton1 & P. Baddeley
Human Herpes Virus	June 2003 Human Herpes Virus Infection within Families in Rural Tanzania Sam M. Mbulaiteye, Ruth M. Pfeiffer, Denise Whitby, Glen R. Brubaker, John Shao & Robert J. Biggar
Hepatitis A and E	January 2010 Hepatitis E Epidemic, Uganda Eyasu H. Teshale, Christopher M. Howard, Scott P. Grytdal, Thomas R. Handzel, Vaughn Barry, Saleem Kamili, Jan Drobeniuc, Samuel Okware, Robert Downing, Jordan W. Tappero, Barnabas Bakamutumaho, Chong-Gee Teo, John W. Ward, Scott D. Holmberg & Dale J. Hu Emerging Infectious Diseases

The diseases identified above are highly preventable. Some of them were one of the top ten leading causes of morbidity in Cebu City.

Drinking, Sharing of Utensils and Allergic Reactions. In a "tagay" session, serving a food allergen as a "pulutan" is most of the time unavoidable. Even if the participant knew and would not eat the food, there is still a high risk of getting the food allergy since everyone shares a common glass. In the Food Safety and Nutrition portion of Food Insight (2000) quoted:

"Sometimes one can't avoid serving a common food allergen, even when an individual has alerted you to the existence of an allergy. In these cases, it's still possible to have a reaction-free event, but... According to Hefle, measures to take include: ...avoiding cross contact by not sharing utensils..."

If this occur the participant may display: (1) skin symptoms - swelling, hives, eczema/atopic dermatitis (skin rash); (2) gastrointestinal symptoms - abdominal cramps, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea; (3) respiratory symptoms - runny nose, asthma/difficulty breathing, tightening of the throat; (4) oral symptoms - itching, swelling and hives in the mouth, palate and tongue; and (5) systemic symptoms - anaphylactic shock (severe shock involving several body systems). Most of these symptoms presented by Food Insight (2000) are detrimental to health and may cause sudden death.

Nursing Culture Care Repatterning and Restructuring. Leininger (2001) defined repatterning and restructuring to those assistive, supporting, facilitative, or enabling professional actions and decisions that help a clients reorder, change, or greatly modify their lifeways. To establish new, different, and beneficial health care patterns while respecting the clients cultural values and beliefs. This still provides a beneficial or healthier lifeway than before the changes were co-established with the clients.

This is the main objective of the researcher, to restructure and repattern certain procedures in the Cebuano "tagay". This will prevent communicable diseases and cross contact food allergies.

In summary, nurses who understand and value the practice of culturally competent care are able to effect positive changes in healthcare practices for clients of designated cultures. Leininger (2002, 1991 as cited by Sitzman & Wright, 2003) emphasized that sharing a cultural identity requires knowledge of transcultural nursing concepts and principles, along with an awareness of current research findings. Further quoted:

"Culturally competent nursing care can only occur when client beliefs and values are thoughtfully and skillfully incorporated into nursing care plans. Caring is the core of nursing. Culturally competent nursing guides the nurse to provide optimal holistic, culturally based care. These practices also help the client to care for himself and others within a familiar, supportive, and meaningful cultural context... Commitment to learning and practicing culturally competent care offers great satisfaction and many other rewards to those who can provide holistic supportive care to all patients"

HEALTH TEACHING PLAN

PURPOSE: To provide awareness about the risk of acquiring communicable diseases in sharing a common glass during the practice of "tagay"

Objectives	Content Outline	Method of Instructions	Time Allotted (in min.)	Resources	Evaluation
After 1 hour of health teaching session, the participant will be able to:					
1. Explain to the respondents the nature and purpose of health teaching regarding "tagay".		Lecture, illustrations	5 minutes	Visual aids	Feedbacks
2. Discuss to the respondents how they practice "tagay".	The rotating glass Cultural values: "pakika-uban" "ulaw" "rispitu"	Demonstration and modelling	10 minutes	Props and appropriate materials needed	Demonstration
3. To be able to discuss the associated risk of acquiring communicable diseases of rotating glass.	Risk of acquiring the different communicable diseases and cross contact allergen contamination	Lecture and illustration	20 minutes	AV Presentation (Documentary and Advertisement)	Feedbacks and question and answer portion
4. To be able to discuss the means of getting rid of the risk.	Avoid sharing a common glass or utensils Handwashing Benefits of avoiding the use of a common glass or utensils	Lecture and illustration	5 minutes	AV Presentation (Documentary and Advertisement)	Feedbacks and question and answer.
5. Explain to the respondents			10 minutes	AV Presentation (Documentary and Advertisement)	Feedbacks and question and answer.

Note: Contents of the health teaching guide were translated in a video advertisement format.

Conclusion

Culturally, Cebuanos use a common glass in drinking sessions to display the system of the collective "I". Metasynthesis results revealed that this practice can harbor cross contact contamination that is detrimental to health. Cross contact contamination in a form of a viral or bacterial infection, or allergen that is unawaresly communicated thru a fomite (the common glass). Utilizing the concepts of Culture Care Repatterning and Restructuring, interventions are required to change the practice of sharing a common glass to reduce risks for acquiring communicable diseases or cross contact allergies.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were drafted:

1. Health teaching in the classroom and community setting must focus on the modification of the practice by:
 - a. using individual glasses and avoid sharing;
 - b. passing the bottle instead of the glass to preserve the cultural value of "pakigka-uban" while preventing communicable diseases and cross contact allergen contamination.
2. An AV Advertisement and/or Documentary containing the contents of the health teaching plan can be promoted in TV Networks when funded; and
3. Further studies should be done specifically on the cases of communicable diseases and cross contact allergic reactions caused by sharing a common glass.

References

- Abedon, S. (2009). Supplemental Lecture: Acquisition of Disease. Retrieved last March 30, 2010 from <http://www.mansfield.ohio-state.edu/~sabedon/biol2050.htm>
- Agoncillo, T., & Guerrero, M. (1987). *History of the Filipino People*. Quezon City, Philippines: Garcia Publishing Company.
- Allgood, M.R. and Tomey, A. M. (2002). *Nursing theory utilization & application* (2nd ed.). St. Louis, Missouri: Mosby.
- Boholst, F. (2006). "Emphasizing the "I" in Us: The Filipino Psychology", Plenary Session in the Cebu Psychology Convention entitled *Redefining Identity: Exploring the diversity of Psychology*. Cebu City, Philippines.
- Calago, M. (2009). Retrieved last February 10, 2010 from www.blogcatalog.com/topic/sharing-glass-and-health
- Center for Disease Control and Prevention (2010). *CDC Guidance on Helping Child Care and Early Childhood Programs Respond to Influenza during the 2009-2010 Influenza Season*. Retrieved last February 11, 2010 from www.state.nj.us/humanservices/emergency/childcare_guidance.pdf
- Department of Health and Human Services: Center for Control and Prevention (2005). *Infection Control Recommendations for Prevention of Transmission of Diarrheal Diseases in Evacuation*.
- Duff, M., Scheepers, M., Cooper, M., Hoghton, M. & Baddeley, P. (2001). *Helicobacter pylori: Has the killer escaped from the institution? A possible cause of increased stomach cancer in a population with intellectual disability*. *Journal of Intellectual Disability Research*. Volume 45 Part 3 pp 219-225
- Dwyer, J.M. (2006). *Access to Health Care Among Mexican and Central American Migrant Workers in Northwest Florida: Description of Needed Care and Barriers*. Masters of Science in Nursing Thesis, The Florida State University, Fall Semester 2006.
- Enriquez, V. (1994). *From colonial to liberation psychology: The Philippine experience*. Manila, Philippines: De La Salle University Press.
- Fingfeld, D. (2003). *Metasynthesis: The state of the the art-so far*. *Qualitative Health Research*, 13(7), 893-904
- Food Insights (2000). *Current Topics in Food Safety and Nutrition: Food Allergy Symptoms*. Food Insights. July/August 2000.
- Giger, J.N., & Davidhizar, R.E. (2004). *Transcultural Nursing: Assessment and Intervention* (4th ed.). St. Louis C. V. Mosby.
- Gopez-Cervantes, J. (2009). *Drinking habit taking its toll on Pinoy's health*. *Philippine Star: Health and Medicine*.
- Handford County Health Department (nd). *Facts about Meningitis*. Retrieved last February 11, 2010 from www.harfordcountymd.gov/Health/Download/593.pdf
- Heath, D.B. (1991). *Women and alcohol: Cross-cultural perspectives*. *Journal Of Substance Abuse*, 3: 175-185.
- Heath, D.B. (1992). *Ethnic classifications in alcohol studies are 'garbled'* (Letter). *Addiction*, 8(3): 3.
- iGuide Interactive Travel Guide. (2009). *Drinking in Philippines*. Retrieved last April 2, 2009 from <http://iguide.travel/Philippines/Drinking>.

- Jocano, F.L. (1997). *Anthropology of the Filipino People IV*. Metro Manila : Punlad Research House.
- Kagiharab, L.E., Niederhauser, V.P. & Stark, S. (2009). Assessment, management, and prevention of early childhood caries. *Journal of the American Academy of Nurse Practitioners*. 21: 1-10
- Kozier, B., Erb G, Berman A., & Snyder S. (2004). *Fundamentals of Nursing: Concepts, Process, and Practice* (7th ed.). NJ: Pearson Education Incorporated.
- Leininger, M.M. (2006). Part I. The Theory of Care and the Ethnonursing Research Method. *Transcultural Nursing* (pp. 71-98; 3rd ed.). International Edition: McGraw-Hill Companies, Inc.
- Leininger, M.M. (Ed.). (2001). *Culture Care Diversity and Universality: A Theory of Nursing*. New York: National League for Nursing Press.
- Leininger, M.M., & McFarland, M. (2002). *Transcultural Nursing: Concepts, Theories, Research, and Practice* (3rd ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill. Polit, D.F. and Beck, C.T. (2004). *Nursing Research: Principles and Methods*. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins.
- Llora, M. (2004). *Philippine Values: An Interdisciplinary Examination*.
- Longworth, D. L. (2001). *Handbook of Infectious Diseases*. Springhouse. Lynch, Frank (1968). *Four Readings on Philippine Values*. Quezon City: Ateneo de Manila, Philippines University Press.
- Lynch, F. (1968). *Four Readings on Philippine Values*. Quezon City: Ateneo de Manila, Philippines University Press.
- McBride, M. (2001). *Health and Health Care of Filipino American Elders*. Stanford Geriatric Education Center, Stanford University School of Medicine, Stanford, California.
- MDCH (2008). *Vaccine-Preventable Disease Investigation Guidelines - Pertussis*
- *Meningococcal Disease* (2009). *Meningococcal Disease: Information for the Public*. Retrieved last February 11, 2010 from <http://www.immunize.org/vis/menin05.pdf>
- National Statistics Office, Republic of the Philippines (2007). *Cebu City Census of Population as of August 1, 2007*.
- Ngadaya, E.S., Mfinanga, G.S., Wandwalo, E.R., & Morkve, O. (2009). Delay in Tuberculosis case detection in Pwani region, Tanzania. A cross sectional study. *BMC Health Services Research*, 9:196 doi:10.1186/1472-6963-9-196
- Ohuabunwo, C., Perevoscikovs, J., Griskevica, A., Gargiullo, P., Brilla, A., Viksna, L., Glismann, S., Wharton, M. & Vitek, C (2005). Respiratory diphtheria among highly vaccinated military trainees in Latvia: Improved protection from DT compared with Td booster vaccination. *Scandinavian Journal of Infectious Diseases*. 37: 813_/820
- Polit, D.F. and Beck, C.T. (2008). *Nursing Research: Generating an Evidence-Based Practice*. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins.
- Queensland Health, Queensland Government (nd). *Community Group Manual: Gastroenteritis Outbreaks in Camp Facilities - Preventive Group Management*.
- Reyes, J. (2004). Tagay (Story 1). Retrieved last December 20, 2009 from <http://www.zambalesforum.org/Tagay.htm>
- Rodel, P.A. (2002). *Culture and Customs of the Philippines: Cuisine and Fashion*. Westport, Connecticut: Greenwood Press
- Shives, L.R. (2008). *Basic Concepts of Psychiatric-Mental Health Nursing* (7th ed.). Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- Sitzman K. & Wright Eichelberger L. (2003). *Understanding the Work of Nurse Theorists: A Creative Beginning*. Sudbury, Massachusetts: Jones and Bartlette Publishers, Inc.
- Smeltzer, S., Bare, B., Hinkle, J., Cheever, K. (2008). *Brunner & Suddarth's Textbook of Medical-Surgical Nursing* (11th ed.). Library of Congress - Cataloguing in Publication Data. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- Sundkvist T, Hamilton GR, Hourihan BM & Hart IJ (2000). Outbreak of hepatitis A spread by contaminated drinking glasses in a public house. *Communicable Disease and Public Health*. 3:1
- Tan, M. (2009). Let's Drink to That! *Philippine Daily Inquirer*. Retrieved last February 10, 2010 from http://showbizandstyle.inquirer.net/sundaymagazine/sundayinqmag/view_article.php?article_id=216104
- Teshale, E.H., Howard, C.M., Grytdal, S.P., Handzel, T.R., Barry, V., Kamili, S., Drobeniuc, J., Okware, S., Downing, R., Tappero, J.W., Bakamutumaho, B., Teo, C.G., Ward, J.W., Holmberg, S.D. & Hu, D.J. (2010). Hepatitis E Epidemic, Uganda. *Emerging Infectious Diseases*. 16:1
- The Social Issues Research Centre (1998). *Social and Cultural Aspects of Drinking: A report to the Amsterdam Group*.
- Valbuena, J.P. (2001). Alcohol and media: The Situation in the Philippines. *The Globe*, 4(3 & 4), 12-15
- Washington State Department of Health (2008). *Mumps*. Retrieved last October 18, 2009 from www.doh.wa.gov/notify/guidelines/pdf/mumps.pdf
- Wong, S.Y., Lim, W.W.C., Que, T.L. & Au, D.M.Y. (2005). Reflection on SARS precautions in a severe intellectual disabilities hospital in Hong Kong. *Journal of Intellectual Disability Research*. Volume 49, Part 5
- Yambio, C. (2004). *The Ebola Crisis*. Retrieved last February 11, 2010 from <http://www.who.int/csr/don/en/EbolaLeafletEnglish.pdf>